

**A QUANTITATIVE APPROACH TO TIME SERIES
FORECASTING**

PROJECT REPORT

ABSTRACT

This project presents a new approach to forecast the behavior of time series based on similarity of pattern sequences. First, clustering techniques are used with the aim of grouping and labeling the samples from a dataset. Thus, the prediction of a data point is provided as follows. First, the pattern sequence prior to the day to be predicted is extracted. Then, this sequence is searched in the historical data and the prediction is calculated by averaging all the samples immediately after the matched sequence. The main novelty is that only the labels associated with each pattern are considered to forecast the future behavior of the time series, avoiding the use of real values of the time series until the last step of the prediction process. Results from several energy time series are reported and the performance of the proposed method is compared to that of recently published techniques showing a remarkable improvement in the prediction.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1. LBS – Location Based Services
2. LS – Location Server
3. ORT – Object R- Tree (at the LS)
4. K – Anonymity degree
5. NAP – Network Anonymization process.
6. kNN – k Nearest Neighbour
7. $d_N(u,o)$ – Network distance from user u to object o
8. B – Total number of user buckets (for a given k)
9. b_i – Total i^{th} bucket of user (for a given k)
10. PSF - Pattern Sequence-based Forecasting

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of temporal data and the prediction of future values of time series are among the most important problems that data analysts face in many fields, ranging from finance and economics, to production operations management or telecommunications. A forecast is a prediction of some future event(s). Forecasting problems are often classified as short-term, medium-term, and long-term. Short-term forecasting problems involve predicting events only a few time periods (days, weeks, months) into the future. Medium-term forecasts extend from one to two years and long-term forecasting problems can extend beyond that by many years. Time series data can be defined as a chronological sequence of observations on a variable of interest. Most forecasting problems imply the use of such data whose analysis has traditionally been done by means of classical statistical tools. Nowadays, data mining techniques are acquiring a great relevance due to the large number of samples forming the time series in multiple areas. A new approach, called Pattern Sequence-based Forecasting (PSF), is here presented in order to forecast time series. This work can be considered a generalization of the algorithm introduced in [1], which is based on nearest neighbors techniques. Nevertheless, the new approach makes predictions using only labels generated by means of clustering techniques. This fact discretizes and simplifies the process of prediction, since during the whole process, the PSF algorithm deals with sequences of labels instead of with sets of real values. Despite that a naive use of labels to predict time series was presented in [2], the PSF includes a new methodology to automatize the obtaining of the labels providing rules to assign them to the samples of real values. The sensitivity of the key parameter involved in the selection of the number of underlying patterns is also analyzed in order to study the robustness of the method. The number of labels comprising the pattern sequence, used in each prediction process, is systematically determined in this work.

The PSF algorithm aims to be a general-purpose forecasting procedure. However, Share-related problems are addressed in this work. To be precise, two major groups of time series are forecasted: Share values changes and Buyers requirements. These groups belong to three different Sectors: Information Technology, Pharmaceutical and Banking . Therefore, the overall experimentation consists of six independent time series showing thus the

adaptability of the PSF to miscellaneous time series. Moreover, in order to facilitate the comparison of the obtained results, all the data sets analyzed are available online .The rest of the paper is organized as follows: presents an exhaustive revision of the state of the art on share change and buyer requirement of time series forecasting. Introduces the proposed methodology and the description of the PSF algorithm, which can be applied to time series of any nature. The following chapter shows the results obtained by the PSF approach in share markets of India for the month October 2011, including measures of the quality of them. In comparisons between the proposed method and other techniques are provided. Finally, summarizes the main conclusions achieved and gives clues for future work.

1.1 An Overview of Data Mining Techniques

Introduction

This overview provides a description of some of the most common data mining algorithms in use today. We have broken the discussion into two sections, each with a specific theme:

- Classical Techniques: Statistics, Neighborhoods and Clustering
- Next Generation Techniques: Trees, Networks and Rules

Each section will describe a number of data mining algorithms at a high level, focusing on the "big picture" so that the reader will be able to understand how each algorithm fits into the landscape of data mining techniques. Overall, six broad classes of data mining algorithms are covered. Although there are a number of other algorithms and many variations of the techniques described, one of the algorithms from this group of six is almost always used in real world deployments of data mining systems.

1.2 Classical Techniques: Statistics, Neighborhoods and Clustering

The Classics

These two sections have been broken up based on when the data mining technique was developed and when it became technically mature enough to be used for business, especially for aiding in the optimization of customer relationship management systems. Thus this section contains descriptions of techniques that have classically been used for decades the next section represents techniques that have only been widely used since the early 1980s.

This section should help the user to understand the rough differences in the techniques and at least enough information to be dangerous and well armed enough to not be baffled by the vendors of different data mining tools.

The main techniques that we will discuss here are the ones that are used 99.9% of the time on existing business problems. There are certainly many other ones as well as proprietary techniques from particular vendors - but in general the industry is converging to those techniques that work consistently and are understandable and explainable.

Statistics

By strict definition "statistics" or statistical techniques are not data mining. They were being used long before the term data mining was coined to apply to business applications. However, statistical techniques are driven by the data and are used to discover patterns and build predictive models. And from the users perspective you will be faced with a conscious choice when solving a "data mining" problem as to whether you wish to attack it with statistical methods or other data mining techniques. For this reason it is important to have some idea of how statistical techniques work and how they can be applied.

What is different between statistics and data mining?

I flew the Boston to Newark shuttle recently and sat next to a professor from one the Boston area Universities. He was going to discuss the drosophila (fruit flies) genetic makeup to a pharmaceutical company in New Jersey. He had compiled the world's largest database on the genetic makeup of the fruit fly and had made it available to other researchers on the internet through Java applications accessing a larger relational database.

He explained to me that they not only now were storing the information on the flies but also were doing "data mining" adding as an aside "which seems to be very important these days whatever that is". I mentioned that I had written a book on the subject and he was interested in knowing what the difference was between "data mining" and statistics. There was no easy answer.

The techniques used in data mining, when successful, are successful for precisely the same reasons that statistical techniques are successful (e.g. clean data, a well defined target to predict and good validation to avoid over fitting). And for the most part the techniques are used in the same places for the same types of problems (prediction, classification discovery).

In fact some of the techniques that are classical defined as "data mining" such as CART and CHAID arose from statisticians.

So what is the difference? Why aren't we as excited about "statistics" as we are about data mining? There are several reasons. The first is that the classical data mining techniques such as CART, neural networks and nearest neighbor techniques tend to be more robust to both messier real world data and also more robust to being used by less expert users. But that is not the only reason. The other reason is that the time is right. Because of the use of computers for closed loop business data storage and generation there now exists large quantities of data that is available to users. IF there were no data - there would be no interest in mining it. Likewise the fact that computer hardware has dramatically upped the ante by several orders of magnitude in storing and processing the data makes some of the most powerful data mining techniques feasible today.

The bottom line though, from an academic standpoint at least, is that there is little practical difference between a statistical technique and a classical data mining technique. Hence we have included a description of some of the most useful in this section.

What is statistics?

Statistics is a branch of mathematics concerning the collection and the description of data. Usually statistics is considered to be one of those scary topics in college right up there with chemistry and physics. However, statistics is probably a much friendlier branch of mathematics because it really can be used every day. Statistics was in fact born from very humble beginnings of real world problems from business, biology, and gambling!

Knowing statistics in your everyday life will help the average business person make better decisions by allowing them to figure out risk and uncertainty when all the facts either aren't known or can't be collected. Even with all the data stored in the largest of data warehouses business decisions still just become more informed guesses. The more and better the data and the better the understanding of statistics the better the decision that can be made.

Statistics has been around for a long time easily a century and arguably many centuries when the ideas of probability began to gel. It could even be argued that the data collected by the ancient Egyptians, Babylonians, and Greeks were all statistics long before the field was officially recognized. Today data mining has been defined independently of statistics though "mining data" for patterns and predictions is really what statistics is all about. Some of the techniques that are classified under data mining such as CHAID and

CART really grew out of the statistical profession more than anywhere else, and the basic ideas of probability, independence and causality and overfitting are the foundation on which both data mining and statistics are built.

Data, counting and probability

One thing that is always true about statistics is that there is always data involved, and usually enough data so that the average person cannot keep track of all the data in their heads. This is certainly more true today than it was when the basic ideas of probability and statistics were being formulated and refined early this century. Today people have to deal with up to terabytes of data and have to make sense of it and glean the important patterns from it. Statistics can help greatly in this process by helping to answer several important questions about your data:

- What patterns are there in my database?
- What is the chance that an event will occur?
- Which patterns are significant?
- What is a high level summary of the data that gives me some idea of what is contained in my database?

Certainly statistics can do more than answer these questions but for most people today these are the questions that statistics can help answer. Consider for example that a large part of statistics is concerned with summarizing data, and more often than not, this summarization has to do with counting. One of the great values of statistics is in presenting a high level view of the database that provides some useful information without requiring every record to be understood in detail. This aspect of statistics is the part that people run into every day when they read the daily newspaper and see, for example, a pie chart reporting the number of US citizens of different eye colors, or the average number of annual doctor visits for people of different ages. Statistics at this level is used in the reporting of important information from which people may be able to make useful decisions. There are many different parts of statistics but the idea of collecting data and counting it is often at the base of even these more sophisticated techniques. The first step then in understanding statistics is to understand how the data is collected into a higher level form - one of the most notable ways of doing this is with the histogram.

Histograms

One of the best ways to summarize data is to provide a histogram of the data. In the simple example database shown in Table 1.1 we can create a histogram of eye color by counting the number of occurrences of different colors of eyes in our database. For this example database of 10 records this is fairly easy to do and the results are only slightly more interesting than the database itself. However, for a database of many more records this is a very useful way of getting a high level understanding of the database.

ID	Name	Prediction	Age	Balance	Income	Eyes	Gender
1	Amy	No	62	\$0	Medium	Brown	F
2	Al	No	53	\$1,800	Medium	Green	M
4	Bob	Yes	32	\$45	Medium	Green	M

This histogram shown in figure 1.1 depicts a simple predictor (eye color) which will have only a few different values no matter if there are 100 customer records in the database or 100 million. There are, however, other predictors that have many more distinct values and can create a much more complex histogram. Consider, for instance, the histogram of ages of the customers in the population. In this case the histogram can be more complex but can also be enlightening. Consider if you found that the histogram of your customer data looked as it does in figure 1.2.

Figure 1.1 Histogram 1

Figure 1.1 This histogram shows the number of customers with various eye colors. This summary can quickly show important information about the database such as that blue eyes are the most frequent.

Figure 1.2 Histogram 2

Figure 1.2 This histogram shows the number of customers of different ages and quickly tells the viewer that the majority of customers are over the age of 50.

By looking at this second histogram the viewer is in many ways looking at all of the data in the database for a particular predictor or data column. By looking at this histogram it is also possible to build an intuition about other important factors. Such as the average age of

the population, the maximum and minimum age. All of which are important. These values are called summary statistics. Some of the most frequently used summary statistics include:

- Max - the maximum value for a given predictor.
- Min - the minimum value for a given predictor.
- Mean - the average value for a given predictor.
- Median - the value for a given predictor that divides the database as nearly as possible into two databases of equal numbers of records.
- Mode - the most common value for the predictor.
- Variance - the measure of how spreads out the values are from the average value.

When there are many values for a given predictor the histogram begins to look smoother and smoother (compare the difference between the two histograms above). Sometimes the shape of the distribution of data can be calculated by an equation rather than just represented by the histogram. This is what is called a data distribution. Like a histogram a data distribution can be described by a variety of statistics. In classical statistics the belief is that there is some “true” underlying shape to the data distribution that would be formed if all possible data was collected. The shape of the data distribution can be calculated for some simple examples. The statistician’s job then is to take the limited data that may have been collected and from that make their best guess at what the “true” or at least most likely underlying data distribution might be.

Many data distributions are well described by just two numbers, the mean and the variance. The mean is something most people are familiar with, the variance, however, can be problematic. The easiest way to think about it is that it measures the average distance of each predictor value from the mean value over all the records in the database. If the variance is high it implies that the values are all over the place and very different. If the variance is low most of the data values are fairly close to the mean. To be precise the actual definition of the variance uses the square of the distance rather than the actual distance from the mean and the average is taken by dividing the squared sum by one less than the total number of records. In terms of prediction a user could make some guess at the value of a predictor without knowing anything else just by knowing the mean and also gain some basic sense of how variable the guess might be based on the variance.

1.3 Statistics for Prediction

In this book the term “prediction” is used for a variety of types of analysis that may elsewhere be more precisely called regression. We have done so in order to simplify some of the concepts and to emphasize the common and most important aspects of predictive modeling. Nonetheless regression is a powerful and commonly used tool in statistics and it will be discussed here.

1.4 Linear regression

In statistics prediction is usually synonymous with regression of some form. There are a variety of different types of regression in statistics but the basic idea is that a model is created that maps values from predictors in such a way that the lowest error occurs in making a prediction. The simplest form of regression is simple linear regression that just contains one predictor and a prediction. The relationship between the two can be mapped on a two dimensional space and the records plotted for the prediction values along the Y axis and the predictor values along the X axis. The simple linear regression model then could be viewed as the line that minimized the error rate between the actual prediction value and the point on the line (the prediction from the model). Graphically this would look as it does in Figure 1.3. The simplest form of regression seeks to build a predictive model that is a line that maps between each predictor value to a prediction value. Of the many possible lines that could be drawn through the data the one that minimizes the distance between the line and the data points is the one that is chosen for the predictive model.

On average if you guess the value on the line it should represent an acceptable compromise amongst all the data at that point giving conflicting answers. Likewise if there is no data available for a particular input value the line will provide the best guess at a reasonable answer based on similar data.

Figure 1.3 Linear regression

Figure 1.3 Linear regression is similar to the task of finding the line that minimizes the total distance to a set of data.

The predictive model is the line shown in Figure 1.3. The line will take a given value for a predictor and map it into a given value for a prediction. The actual equation would look something like: $\text{Prediction} = a + b * \text{Predictor}$. Which is just the equation for a line $Y = a + bX$. As an example for a bank the predicted average consumer bank balance might equal $\$1,000 + 0.01 * \text{customer's annual income}$. The trick, as always with predictive modeling, is to find the model that best minimizes the error. The most common way to calculate the error is the square of the difference between the predicted value and the actual value. Calculated this way points that are very far from the line will have a great effect on moving the choice of line towards themselves in order to reduce the error. The values of a and b in the regression equation that minimize this error can be calculated directly from the data relatively quickly.

What if the pattern in my data doesn't look like a straight line?

Regression can become more complicated than the simple linear regression we've introduced so far. It can get more complicated in a variety of different ways in order to better model particular database problems. There are, however, three main modifications that can be made

1. More predictors than just one can be used.
2. Transformations can be applied to the predictors.
3. Predictors can be multiplied together and used as terms in the equation.
4. Modifications can be made to accommodate response predictions that just have yes/no or 0/1 values.

Adding more predictors to the linear equation can produce more complicated lines that take more information into account and hence make a better prediction. This is called multiple linear regression and might have an equation like the following if 5 predictors were used (X1, X2, X3, X4, X5):

$$Y = a + b_1(X_1) + b_2(X_2) + b_3(X_3) + b_4(X_4) + b_5(X_5)$$

This equation still describes a line but it is now a line in a 6 dimensional space rather than the two dimensional space.

By transforming the predictors by squaring, cubing or taking their square root it is possible to use the same general regression methodology and now create much more complex models that are no longer simple shaped like lines. This is called non-linear regression. A model of just one predictor might look like this: $Y = a + b_1(X_1) + b_2(X_1^2)$. In many real world cases analysts will perform a wide variety of transformations on their data just to try them out. If they do not contribute to a useful model their coefficients in the equation will tend toward zero and then they can be removed. The other transformation of predictor values that is often performed is multiplying them together. For instance a new predictor created by dividing hourly wage by the minimum wage might be a much more effective predictor than hourly wage by itself.

When trying to predict a customer response that is just yes or no (e.g. they bought the product or they didn't or they defaulted or they didn't) the standard form of a line doesn't work. Since there are only two possible values to be predicted it is relatively easy to fit a line through them. However, that model would be the same no matter what predictors were being used or what particular data was being used. Typically in these situations a transformation of the prediction values is made in order to provide a better predictive model. This type of regression is called logistic regression and because so many business problems are response

problems, logistic regression is one of the most widely used statistical techniques for creating predictive models.

1.5 Nearest Neighbor

Clustering and the Nearest Neighbor prediction technique are among the oldest techniques used in data mining. Most people have an intuition that they understand what clustering is - namely that like records are grouped or clustered together. Nearest neighbor is a prediction technique that is quite similar to clustering - its essence is that in order to predict what a prediction value is in one record look for records with similar predictor values in the historical database and use the prediction value from the record that is “nearest” to the unclassified record.

A simple example of clustering

A simple example of clustering would be the clustering that most people perform when they do the laundry - grouping the permanent press, dry cleaning, whites and brightly colored clothes is important because they have similar characteristics. And it turns out they have important attributes in common about the way they behave (and can be ruined) in the wash. To “cluster” your laundry most of your decisions are relatively straightforward. There are of course difficult decisions to be made about which cluster your white shirt with red stripes goes into (since it is mostly white but has some color and is permanent press). When clustering is used in business the clusters are often much more dynamic - even changing weekly to monthly and many more of the decisions concerning which cluster a record falls into can be difficult.

A simple example of nearest neighbor

A simple example of the nearest neighbor prediction algorithm is that if you look at the people in your neighborhood (in this case those people that are in fact geographically near to you). You may notice that, in general, you all have somewhat similar incomes. Thus if your neighbor has an income greater than \$100,000 chances are good that you too have a high income. Certainly the chances that you have a high income are greater when all of your neighbors have incomes over \$100,000 than if all of your neighbors have incomes of \$20,000. Within your neighborhood there may still be a wide variety of incomes possible among even your “closest” neighbors but if you had to predict someone’s income based on

only knowing their neighbors you're best chance of being right would be to predict the incomes of the neighbors who live closest to the unknown person.

The nearest neighbor prediction algorithm works in very much the same way except that "nearness" in a database may consist of a variety of factors not just where the person lives. It may, for instance, be far more important to know which school someone attended and what degree they attained when predicting income. The better definition of "near" might in fact be other people that you graduated from college with rather than the people that you live next to.

Nearest Neighbor techniques are among the easiest to use and understand because they work in a way similar to the way that people think - by detecting closely matching examples. They also perform quite well in terms of automation, as many of the algorithms are robust with respect to dirty data and missing data. Lastly they are particularly adept at performing complex ROI calculations because the predictions are made at a local level where business simulations could be performed in order to optimize ROI. As they enjoy similar levels of accuracy compared to other techniques the measures of accuracy such as lift are as good as from any other.

How to use Nearest Neighbor for Prediction

One of the essential elements underlying the concept of clustering is that one particular object (whether they be cars, food or customers) can be closer to another object than can some third object. It is interesting that most people have an innate sense of ordering placed on a variety of different objects. Most people would agree that an apple is closer to an orange than it is to a tomato and that a Toyota Corolla is closer to a Honda Civic than to a Porsche. This sense of ordering on many different objects helps us place them in time and space and to make sense of the world. It is what allows us to build clusters - both in databases on computers as well as in our daily lives. This definition of nearness that seems to be ubiquitous also allows us to make predictions.

The nearest neighbor prediction algorithm simply stated is:

Objects that are "near" to each other will have similar prediction values as well. Thus if you know the prediction value of one of the objects you can predict it for its nearest neighbors.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Abraham and B. Nath, “A Neuro-Fuzzy Approach for Forecasting Electricity Demand in Victoria,” *Applied Soft Computing J.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 127-138, 2001.

Hybrid intelligent systems are becoming a very important problem solving methodology affecting researchers and practitioners in areas ranging from science, technology, business and commerce. It is well known that intelligent systems, which can provide human-like expertise such as domain knowledge, uncertain reasoning, and adaptation to a noisy and time-varying environment, are important in tackling practical computing problems.

Main research is on developing advanced intelligent systems using hybrid natural computation techniques. Research in natural computation includes a theoretical and empirical understanding of computing inspired from nature. Hybridization of different intelligent systems is an innovative approach to construct computationally intelligent systems consisting of artificial neural network, fuzzy inference systems, rough set, approximate reasoning and derivative free optimization methods such as evolutionary computation, swarm intelligence, bacterial foraging and so on. The integration of different learning and adaptation techniques, to overcome individual limitations and achieve synergetic effects through hybridization or fusion of these techniques, has in recent years contributed to a large number of new intelligent system designs.

We are already aware of several hybrid combinations like evolutionary computation-neural network, neural network - fuzzy inference system, fuzzy inference system-evolutionary computation, neural network- fuzzy inference system-evolutionary computation and so on.

S.K. Aggarwal, L.M. Saini, and A. Kumar, “Electricity Price Forecasting in Deregulated Markets: A Review and Evaluation,” *Int’l J. Electrical Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 13-22, 2009.

This paper presents a new approach to forecast the behavior of time series based on similarity of pattern sequences. First, clustering techniques are used with the aim of grouping and labeling the samples from a data set. Thus, the prediction of a data point is provided as follows: first, the pattern sequence prior to the day to be predicted is extracted. Then, this sequence is searched in the historical data and the prediction is calculated by averaging all the samples immediately after the matched sequence. The main novelty is that only the labels associated with each pattern are considered to forecast the future behavior of the time series, avoiding the use of real values of the time series until the last step of the prediction process. Results from several energy time series are reported and the performance of the proposed method is compared to that of recently published techniques showing a remarkable improvement in the prediction.

N. Amjady, “Day-Ahead Price Forecasting of Electricity Markets by a New Fuzzy Neural Network,” *IEEE Trans. Power Systems*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 887-896, May 2006.

In this paper, an efficient method based on a new fuzzy neural network is proposed for short-term price forecasting of electricity markets. This fuzzy neural network has inter-layer and feed-forward architecture with a new hypercubic training mechanism. The proposed method predicts hourly market-clearing prices for the day-ahead electricity markets. By combination of fuzzy logic and an efficient learning algorithm, an appropriate model for the nonstationary behavior and outliers of the price series is presented. The proposed method is examined on the Spanish electricity market. It is shown that the method can provide more accurate results than the other price forecasting techniques, such as ARIMA time series, wavelet-ARIMA, MLP, and RBF neural networks

J.P.S. Catalao, S.J.P.S. Mariano, V.M.F. Mendes, and L.A.F.M. Ferreira, “Short-Term Electricity Prices Forecasting in a Competitive Market: A Neural Network Approach,” *Electric PowerSystems Research*, vol. 77, pp. 1297-1304, 2007.

This paper provides a two-stage stochastic programming approach for the development of optimal offering strategies for wind power producers. Uncertainty is related to electricity market prices and wind power production. A hybrid intelligent approach, combining wavelet transform, particle swarm optimization and adaptive-network-based fuzzy inference system, is used in this paper to generate plausible scenarios. Also, risk aversion is explicitly modeled using the conditional value-at-risk methodology. Results from a realistic case study, based on a wind farm in Portugal, are provided and analyzed. Finally, conclusions are duly drawn.

D.L. Davies and D.W. Bouldin, “A Cluster Separation Measure,” *IEEE Trans. Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. PAMI-1, no. 2, pp. 224-227, Apr. 1979.

A measure is presented which indicates the similarity of clusters which are assumed to have a data density which is a decreasing function of distance from a vector characteristic of the cluster. The measure can be used to infer the appropriateness of data partitions and can therefore be used to compare relative appropriateness of various divisions of the data. The measure does not depend on either the number of clusters analyzed nor the method of partitioning of the data and can be used to guide a cluster seeking algorithm.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

- The PSF algorithm aims to be a general-purpose forecasting procedure.
- Methodology is divided into two phases clearly differentiated.
- In a first step, a clustering technique is performed
- Second, the phase of forecasting is applied by using the information provided by this clustering.
- The PSF algorithm is focused on predicting samples framed in a time series, either one dimensional or multidimensional previously labeled with clustering techniques

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

- A new forecasting algorithm has been proposed to predict real-world time series
- To Develop a data model with dynamical lengths of window and on smoothing the matching sequence criterion.
- Clustering technique to label 24-dimensional time series has been used and the main novelty lies on the exclusive use of the labels obtained by the clustering to forecast the future behavior of the time series, avoiding the use of the real values of the time series until the last step of the prediction process.

CHAPTER 4

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

4.1 PROBLEM DEFINITION

A time series is a collection of observations of well-defined data items obtained through repeated measurements over time. For example, measuring the value of retail sales each month of the year would comprise a time series. This is because sales revenue is well defined, and consistently measured at equally spaced intervals. Data collected irregularly or only once are not time series. An observed time series can be decomposed into three components: the trend (long term direction), the seasonal (systematic, calendar related movements) and the irregular (unsystematic, short term fluctuations).

Time series can be classified into two different types: stock and flow. A stock series is a measure of certain attributes at a point in time and can be thought of as “stocktakes”. For example, the Monthly Labour Force Survey is a stock measure because it takes stock of whether a person was employed in the reference week. Flow series are series which are a measure of activity over a given period. For example, surveys of Retail Trade activity. Manufacturing is also a flow measure because a certain amount is produced each day, and then these amounts are summed to give a total value for production for a given reporting period. The main difference between a stock and a flow series is that flow series can contain effects related to the calendar (trading day effects). Both types of series can still be seasonally adjusted using the same seasonal adjustment process. A comparison of original data from the same period in each year does not completely remove all seasonal effects. Certain holidays such as Easter and Chinese New Year fall in different periods in each year, hence they will distort observations. Also, year to year values will be biased by any changes in seasonal patterns that occur over time.

4.2 MODULE DESCRIPTION

- Data Set Creation
- Weighted nearest neighbor
- K-means Clustering
- Labeling
- Forecast Report

4.2.1 Data Set Creation

- This is the phase of generating dataset from ICICI Direct.
- We are proposed to collect mutual funds, share details of the companies in Pharmaceutical, Banking and IT industry.

The first task to be completed is the normalization of data that is only used for the clustering process. It can be assumed that the prices increase all along the year following a tendency in accordance with the intra-annual inflation values That is, the original trend is smoothed from the initial data

4.2.2 Weighted Nearest Neighbor

- A modification of the weighted nearest neighbors (WNN) methodology is proposed To be precise, the approach weighted the nearest neighbors in order to improve the prediction accuracy.
- The occurrence of outliers (also called spike prices) or prices significantly higher than the expected values is a usual feature found in these time series. With the aim of dealing with this feature, we proposed a data mining framework based on both support vector machines (SVM) and a probability classifier.
- In practice, W is calculated by means of cross validation. The cross validation was originally defined as: “the statistical practice of partitioning a sample of data into subsets such that the analysis is initially performed on a single subset, while the other

subsets are retained for subsequent use in confirming and validating the initial analysis”

4.2.3 K-means Clustering

Given the database of hourly share change/buyers requirement, the clustering problem consists of identifying K groups or clusters such that the share change/buyers requirement curves of the days belonging to a cluster are similar among them and dissimilar to the curves of those days belonging to other clusters, according to a distance. Clustering is a difficult task due to the great number of possible geometric shapes for the clusters and distances that can be considered.

The K-means algorithm requires that the user provides the number of clusters to be created. However, this number is a priori unknown and its selection and later evaluations of the results obtained by the clustering are crucial for most engineering applications. Thus, the most challenging problem of the clustering realm has been to select the right number of clusters for data sets. For all these reasons, three well-known validity indices have been applied to data in order to decide how many groups the original data set has to be split into: silhouette index, Davies-Bouldin (DB) index, and the Dunn (DU) index. The three of them share a common feature: the new data structure obtained by the clustering algorithm is evaluated to test the validity of the partition

- **K-Means Clustering Technique**
- K-means is a fast method to perform clustering. The basic intuition behind
- K-means is the continuous reassignment of objects into different clusters so that the within-cluster distance is minimized. It uses an iterative algorithm divided in two phases to minimize the sum of point-to-centroid distances, over all K clusters.
- The procedure can be summarized as follows:
 - 1. *Phase 1. In each iteration (evaluation of all the points) every point is reassigned to their closest cluster center. Then the clusters centers are recalculated.*
 - 2. *Phase 2. Points are reassigned only if the sum of distances is reduced. The clusters centers are recalculated after each reassignment.*

4.2.3.1 The Silhouette Index

The silhouette function provides a quality measure of separation among the clusters obtained by using a clustering technique.

The $silh(i)$ can range from -1 to $+1$, where -1 and $+1$ mean that the object i belongs to an adequate and inadequate cluster, respectively. If the silhouette value of the object i belonging to the cluster A is close to zero, it means that the object i can also be in the nearest neighbor cluster to A . If cluster A is a set with only one element, the silhouette value of the object i is not defined and in this case, it is concerted to be equal to zero. The objective function is the average of $silh(i)$ over the number of objects to be classified, and the best clustering is reached when this function is maximized.

4.2.3.2 The Dunn Index

One of the most cited indices was proposed .The Dunn index aims to identify clusters with high inter cluster distance and low intra cluster distance. The Dunn index for K clusters C_i with $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$ is defined.

4.2.3.3 The Davies-Bouldin Index

The Davies-Bouldin index identifies as good clusters those compact clusters which are far from each other. Davies- Bouldin index for K clusters with $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$ is defined

4.2.4 Labeling

- The existence of high-quality clusters is guaranteed if the Davies-Bouldin index reaches small values. Therefore, the optimal number of clusters is found when this index is minimized for the data set called labeling
- The previous clustering generates a sequence of labels associated with every day (in Fig. 2, the sequence of numbers are these labels). Now, a sequence of labels is taken into consideration for further steps; concretely, if the day d has to be predicted, the sequence of labels

4.2.5 FORECAST REPORT

- This section is structured as follows: first, the accuracy of the predictions is validated. Thus, the usual quality parameters are presented.
- Second, the PSF approach is trained in order to produce accurate predictions and, for this reason, the election of both W and K is discussed here.
- Finally, a sensitivity analysis of the proposed method with regard to the number of clusters is presented.

In this section, the number of clusters to be generated, as well as the length of the window comprising the sequence of labels that has to be searched along the time series, are presented. 4.2.1 Selecting the Number of Clusters First of all, the number of clusters K has to be chosen and, for this purpose, the 1 month of the year 2011 are considered for training the algorithm. In order to validate the quality of the clusters produced by K-means algorithm, the silhouette, Dunn, and Davies- Bouldin three indices have been used in the experiments. Thus, the optimal value of K is selected from a system based on majority votes. Table 1 summarizes the results obtained by the three indices of cluster validity, in which the numbers in brackets represent the second best values, as described. A further study about the influence of the number of clusters on the results of the prediction is made.

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Our system design and control is targeted towards the implementation of the project. Though the implementation is not as crucial as system design it also requires something's to take care.

5.1 PATTERN SEQUENCE ALGORITHM

Input: Dataset D , number of clusters K , labeled dataset $[L_1, L_2, \dots, L_{d-2}, L_{d-1}]$, length of the window W and Test Set T
Output: Forecasts $\hat{X}(d)$ for all days of T

PSF()

$ES_d \leftarrow \{\}$

$\hat{X}(d) \leftarrow 0$

for each day $d \in T$

$S_W^{d-1} \leftarrow [L_{d-W}, L_{d-W+1}, \dots, L_{d-2}, L_{d-1}]$

for each j such as $X(j) \in D$

$S_W^j \leftarrow [L_{j-W+1}, L_{j-W+2}, \dots, L_{j-1}, L_j]$

if ($S_W^j = S_W^{d-1}$)

$ES_d \leftarrow ES_d \cup j$

for each $j \in ES_d$

$\hat{X}(d) \leftarrow \hat{X}(d) + X(j + 1)$

$\hat{X}(d) \leftarrow \hat{X}(d) / \text{size}(ES_d)$

$D \leftarrow D \triangleright \hat{X}(d)$

$[L_1, L_2, \dots, L_{d-1}, L_d] \leftarrow \text{clustering}(D, K)$

$d \leftarrow d + 1$

return $\hat{X}(d)$ for all days of T

5.2 ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

5.3 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

5.3.1 Level 0

Anonymization process

Figure 5.1 Overall input and output

5.3.2 Level 1 (Input)

Figure 6.2 Input for User

5.3.3 Level 2 (Output)

Figure 6.3 Output by road map and chart

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION & FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

6.1 CONCLUSION

In this project, a new forecasting algorithm has been proposed to predict real-world time series. As previous step to the prediction, a clustering technique to label 24- dimensional time series has been used and the main novelty lies on the exclusive use of the labels obtained by the clustering to forecast the future behaviour of the time series, avoiding the use of the real values of the time series until the last step of the prediction process. Moreover, an automatization of the selection of the critical parameters— K and W—has been proposed. The algorithm has been successfully applied in Share changes and Buyer requirements time series of Indian Share markets providing very competitive results.

Although outside the scope of this research, an important question for any forecasting model is how does the model stand up in an actual trading scenario? Each of these models should be historically tested as if being used for actual trading. Given the same initial capital investment, what is the return for each of these models? What is the maximum drawdown or capital loss for each of these models? If a model has a high return is it due to many steady small gains or is it due to one huge gain surrounded by many losses? These issues revolve around profit and not model accuracy. These are all critical questions that take the forecasting model from academic research into the actual world of trading.

6.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

The performance was accurate in all of them, showing thus the robustness and adaptability of the proposed approach for time series of different nature. This fact is specially remarkable since the approaches found in literature are usually focused on only one specific time series. Future work is focused on adjusting the model with dynamical lengths of window and on smoothing the matching sequence criterion.

CHAPTER 7

APPENDIX

7.1 Source Code

Cluster.JSP

```
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head>
<meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<title>Time Series Forecast</title>
<meta name="keywords" content="" />
<meta name="description" content="" />
<link href="style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="screen" />
</head>
<%@ page import = "java.sql.*" %>
    <%@ page import = "java.util.*" %>
        <%@ page import = "java.text.*" %>

    <body>
<div id="wrapper">
    <div id="header">
        <div id="menu">
            <ul>
                <li class="current_page_item first">
                    <span>
                        <a href="index.html">Home</a>
                    </span>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="compnay.jsp">DataSet</a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="cluster.jsp">Index</a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="clustergroup.jsp">Cluster</a>
                </li>
                <li>
                    <a href="weight.jsp">Weight</a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</body>
</html>
```

```

                <li>
                    <a href="#">Forecast</a>
                </li>
            </ul>
        </div>
        <!-- end #menu -->
    </div>
    <div id="logo">
        <h1><a href="#">Time Series Forecast </a></h1>

    </div>
    <hr />
    <!-- end #logo -->
    <div id="page">
        <div id="content">
            <div class="post">

                <div class="entry">
                    <p>
<%

```

```

Class.forName("sun.jdbc.odbc.JdbcOdbcDriver");
Connection con=DriverManager.getConnection("jdbc:odbc:suresh");
Statement st=con.createStatement();
ResultSet rs=st.executeQuery("select max(cost),min(cost),avg(cost) from
companyshare");int a=0;int b=0;int c=0;
%><h1>The Index</h1><table border="5">
    <th>The Silhouette Index</th>
    <th>The Dunn Index</th><th>The Davies-Bouldin Index</th>
    <%
while(rs.next())
{
    a=rs.getInt(1);
    b=rs.getInt(2);
    c=rs.getInt(3);
}

    int si=(a-b)/b; %><tr>

    <td><%=si%></td>

    <%Statement st2=con.createStatement();
ResultSet rs2=st2.executeQuery("select count(*),min(cost-tos),max(cost-tos) from
companyshare");

```

```
int a1=0;
int b1=0;
int c1=0;
```

```
while(rs2.next())
{
    a1=rs2.getInt(1);
    b1=rs2.getInt(2);
    c1=rs2.getInt(3);
}
```

```
int di=b1/c1+2;
```

```
int fg=(1/a*((b1)*(b1)))+1;
double db=Math.pow(fg,2);
```

```
%>
```

```
<td><%=di%></td>
<td><%=db%></td>
</tr>
```

```
</table>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="post">
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="post">
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="post">
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- end #content -->
```

```
<div id="sidebar">
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- end #sidebar -->
```

```
<div style="clear: both;">&nbsp;  </div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- end #page -->
```

```
<div id="footer">
```

```
<p>Copyright (c) 2011 Sitenam.com. All rights reserved. Design by <a
href="http://www.freecsstemplates.org/">Free CSS Templates</a>.</p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- end #footer -->
```

```
</div>
```

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

Companyshare.jsp

```
-->
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head>
<meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<title>Time Series Forecast</title>
<meta name="keywords" content="" />
<meta name="description" content="" />
<link href="style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="screen" />
</head>
<body>
<div id="wrapper">
  <div id="header">
    <div id="menu">
      <ul>
        <li class="current_page_item first"><span><a
href="index.html">Home</a></span></li>
        <li><a href="compnay.jsp">DataSet</a></li>
        <li><a href="cluster.jsp">Index</a></li>
        <li><a href="clustergroup.jsp">Cluster</a></li>
        <li><a href="weight.jsp">Weight</a></li>
        <li><a href="#">Forecast</a></li>
      </ul>
    </div>
    <!-- end #menu -->
  </div>
  <div id="logo">
    <h1><a href="#">Time Series Forecast </a></h1>
  </div>
  <hr />
  <!-- end #logo -->
  <div id="page">
    <div id="content">
      <div class="post">
        <h2 class="title"><a href="#"> Company Registration</a></h2>
        <div class="entry">
          <p><form method=post action="company1.jsp"><table
border=5>
          <tr><td>Type</td><td><select name="s1"><option
value="Individual">IT</option>
          <option value="Individual">Bank</option>
          <option value="Individual">Parma</option>
          </select></td></tr>
          <tr><td>Comapny Name</td><td><input type="text" name
="t1"/></td></tr>
          <tr><td>Current</td><td><input type="text" name
="t2"/></td></tr>
          <tr><td>change </td><td><input type="text" name
="t3"/></td></tr>
          </table>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</body>
</html>
```

```

name ="t4"/></td></tr>
="t4"/></td></tr>
="t4"/></td></tr>
="t4"/></td></tr>
="t4"/></td></tr>

name="s1"><option value="NSE">NSE</option>
<tr><td>change Percentage</td><td><input type="text"
<tr><td>Open</td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>High</td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>Low</td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>Volume</td><td><input type="text" name

<tr><td>Code</td><td><select
<option value="BSE">BSE</option>
</select></td></tr>

<tr><td><input type=submit value="submit"/></td><td><input type="reset"
value="reset" /></td></tr>
</table></form>
</p>

</div>
</div>
<div class="post">
</div>
<div class="post">
</div>
<div class="post">
</div>
</div>
</div>
<!-- end #content -->
<div id="sidebar">
</div>
<!-- end #sidebar -->
<div style="clear: both;">&nbsp;</div>
</div>
<!-- end #page -->
<div id="footer">
<p>Copyright (c) 2011 Sitenam.com. All rights reserved. Design by <a
href="http://www.freecsstemplates.org/">Free CSS Templates</a>.</p>
</div>
<!-- end #footer -->
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

Company.jsp

```
-->
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head>
<meta http-equiv="content-type" content="text/html; charset=utf-8" />
<title>Time Series Forecast</title>
<meta name="keywords" content="" />
<meta name="description" content="" />
<link href="style.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css" media="screen" />
</head>
<body>
<div id="wrapper">
  <div id="header">
    <div id="menu">
      <ul>
        <li class="current_page_item first"><span><a
href="index.html">Home</a></span></li>
        <li><a href="compnay.jsp">DataSet</a></li>
        <li><a href="cluster.jsp">Index</a></li>
        <li><a href="clustergroup.jsp">Cluster</a></li>
        <li><a href="weight.jsp">Weight</a></li>
        <li><a href="#">Forecast</a></li>
      </ul>
    </div>
    <!-- end #menu -->
  </div>
  <div id="logo">
    <h1><a href="#">Time Series Forecast </a></h1>
  </div>
  <hr />
  <!-- end #logo -->
  <div id="page">
    <div id="content">
      <div class="post">
        <h2 class="title"><a href="#"> Company Registration</a></h2>
        <div class="entry">
          <p><form method=post action="company1.jsp"><table
border=5>
          <tr><td>Type</td><td><select name="s1"><option
value="Individual">IT</option>
          <option value="Individual">ITES</option>
          <option value="Individual">Parma</option>
          </select></td></tr>
          <tr><td>Comapny Name</td><td><input type="text" name
="t1"/></td></tr>
-->
```

```

=>"t2"/></td></tr>
=>"t3"/></td></tr>
name =>"t4"/></td></tr>
=>"t4"/></td></tr>
=>"t4"/></td></tr>
=>"t4"/></td></tr>
=>"t4"/></td></tr>
=>"t4"/></td></tr>

<tr><td>Current</td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>change </td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>change Percentage</td><td><input type="text"
<tr><td>Open</td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>High</td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>Low</td><td><input type="text" name
<tr><td>Volume</td><td><input type="text" name

<tr><td><input type=submit value="submit"/></td><td><input type="reset"
value="reset" /></td></tr>
</table></form>
</p>

</div>
</div>
<div class="post">

</div>
<div class="post">

</div>
<div class="post">

</div>
</div>
</div>
<!-- end #content -->
<div id="sidebar">

</div>
<!-- end #sidebar -->
<div style="clear: both;">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</div>
</div>
<!-- end #page -->
<div id="footer">
<p>Copyright (c) 2011 Sitenam.com. All rights reserved. Design by <a
href="http://www.freecsstemplates.org/">Free CSS Templates</a>.</p>
</div>
<!-- end #footer -->
</div>
</body>
</html>

```

7.2 Sample Screenshots

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a web application. The browser's address bar shows the URL `localhost:1798/forecast/Home.aspx`. The page has a blue header with the title "Time Series Forecast" and a navigation menu with items: Home, Dataset, Index, Cluster, Weight, and Forecast. The "Home" menu item is selected. On the left side, there is a "Login" form with fields for "UserName", "Password", and "Type" (set to "Individual"), and a "SignIn" button. The main content area, titled "Home", contains a welcome message: "Welcome to Time Series Forecast." followed by a paragraph describing a new forecasting approach based on pattern sequences and clustering. Below this, there is a "Latest Updates" section with two news items: "CB Shares hike upto Rs.25/Share ." and "ICICI share announces 12% dividend." An "Update is ready to install" notification bubble is visible in the bottom right corner. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the Start button, several open applications (forecast, Document1, New Tab, Welcome!), and the system tray with the time 1:43 PM.

Welcome!

localhost:1798/forecast/Dataset.aspx

Time Series Forecast

Home **Dataset** Index Cluster Weight Forecast

Forecasting Legends

Reliable stocks, India

Xanther stocks, USA

Company Registration

Welcome! Register Your Company

Type

Company Name

Current

Change

Change Percentage

Open

High

Low

Volume

Index Type

start forecast (Running) ... Document1 - Micros ... New Tab - Google C ... Welcome! - Google ... 1:44 PM

Welcome!

localhost:1798/forecast/Index.aspx

Time Series Forecast

Home Dataset **Index** Cluster Weight Forecast

Forecasting Legends

Reliable stocks, India

Xanther stocks, USA

Index

The Index

The Silhouette Index	The Dunn Index	The Davies-Bouldin Index
1	-1	4.0

start forecast (Running) ... Document1 - Micros... New Tab - Google C... Welcome! - Google ... 1:44 PM

Welcome!

localhost:1798/forecast/Cluster.aspx

Home Dataset Index **Cluster** Weight Forecast

Forecasting Legends

Reliable stocks, India

Xanther stocks, USA

Monger stocks talks, UK

Cluster

Cluster Name:IT

Company Name	Current Value	Change
HCLTECHEQ	392.25	-8.55
DRREDDYEQ	1451.80	-8.40
LUPINEQ	464.45	-7.95
HEXAWAREEQ	83.20	-1.05
INFYEQ	2438.50	-37.40
TCSEQ	1045.95	2.65
WIPROEQ	333.55	3.35

Cluster Name:Bank

Company Name	Current Value	Change
CANBKEQ	424.25	-9.65
SBINEQ	1787.20	-74.40
ICICIBANKEQ	800.95	-38.15
HDFCBANKEQ	448.90	-7.15
ALBKEQ	145.90	-8.70
CANBKEQ	424.25	-9.65
CANBKEQ	424.25	-9.65
CANBKEQ	424.25	-9.65

Cluster Name:Parma

Company Name	Current Value	Change
AUROPHARMAEQ	119.20	-1.50
CIPLAEO	279.85	-4.50

start | forecast (Running) ... | Document1 - Micros... | New Tab - Google C... | Welcome! - Google ... | 1:44 PM

Welcome!

localhost:1798/forecast/Weight.aspx

Home Dataset Index Cluster Weight Forecast

Forecasting Legends

Reliable stocks, India

Xanther stocks, USA

Monger stocks talks, UK

Weight Assignment Table

Company Name	Total No. of Shares	Cost
INFYEQ	2438.50	-37.40
SBINEQ	1787.20	-74.40
DRREDDYEQ	1451.80	-8.40
DRREDDYEQ	1451.80	-8.40
TCSEQ	1045.95	2.65
ICICIBANKEQ	800.95	-38.15
LUPINEQ	464.45	-7.95
LUPINEQ	464.45	-7.95
HDFCBANKEQ	448.90	-7.15
CANBKEQ	424.25	-9.65
HCLTECHEQ	392.25	-8.55
WIPROEQ	333.55	3.35
CIPLAEQ	279.85	-4.50
ALBKEQ	145.90	-8.70
AUROPHARMAEQ	119.20	-1.50
FKONCOEQ	110.50	-2.85
HEXAWAREEQ	83.20	-1.05
11	11.00	11.00

localhost:1798/forecast/Weight.aspx

start forecast (Running) ... Document1 - Micros... New Tab - Google C... Welcome! - Google ... 1:45 PM

Welcome!

localhost:1798/forecast/Forecast.aspx

Time Series Forecast

Home Dataset Index Cluster Weight Forecast

Forecasting Legends

Reliable stocks, India

Xanther stocks, USA

Forecast

Company Name	ForecastValue
INFYEQ	2438.500000
SBINEQ	1787.200000
DRREDDYEQ	1451.800000
TCSEQ	1045.950000
ICICIBANKEQ	800.950000
LUPINEQ	464.450000
HDFCBANKEQ	448.900000
HCLTECHEQ	392.250000
CANBKEQ	341.400000
WIPROEQ	333.550000
CIPLAEQ	279.850000
ALBKEQ	145.900000
AUOPHARMAEQ	119.200000
FKONCOEQ	110.500000
HEXAWAREEQ	83.200000

localhost:1798/forecast/Forecast.aspx

start forecast (Running) ... Document1 - Micros... New Tab - Google C... Welcome! - Google ... 1:45 PM

7.3 ABOUT FORECASTING

Forecasting is the process of making statements about events whose actual outcomes (typically) have not yet been observed. A commonplace example might be **estimation** for some variable of interest at some specified future date. **Prediction** is a similar, but more general term. Both might refer to formal statistical methods employing **time series**, cross-sectional or longitudinal data, or alternatively to less formal judgemental methods. In any case, the data must be up to date in order for the forecast to be as accurate as possible. Usage can differ between areas of application: for example in **hydrology**, the terms "forecast" and "forecasting" are sometimes reserved for estimates of values at certain specific **future** times, while the term "prediction" is used for more general estimates, such as the number of times floods will occur over a long period. **Risk** and **uncertainty** are central to forecasting and prediction; it is generally considered good practice to indicate the degree of uncertainty attaching to forecasts. The process of climate change and increasing energy prices has led to the usage of Egain of buildings. The method uses Forecasting to reduce the energy needed to heat the building, thus reducing the emission of greenhouse gases. Forecasting is used in the practice of Customer Demand Planning in every day business forecasting for manufacturing companies. Forecasting has also been used to predict the development of conflict situations.

Experts in forecasting perform research that use empirical results to gauge the effectiveness of certain forecasting models. Research has shown that there is little difference between the accuracy of forecasts performed by experts knowledgeable of the conflict situation of interest and that performed by individuals who knew much less. Similarly, experts in some studies argue that role thinking does not contribute to the accuracy of the forecast. The discipline of demand planning, also sometimes referred to as supply chain forecasting, embraces both statistical forecasting and a consensus process. An important, albeit often ignored aspect of forecasting, is the relationship it holds with planning. Forecasting can be described as predicting what the future *will* look like, whereas planning predicts what the future should look like. There is no single right forecasting method to use. Selection of a method should be based on your objectives and your conditions (data etc.) A

good place to find a method, is by visiting a selection tree. An example of a selection tree can be found here. Although quantitative analysis can be very precise, it is not always appropriate. Some experts in the field of forecasting have advised against the use of mean square error to compare forecasting methods.

Categories of forecasting methods

1) Qualitative vs. Quantitative Methods

Qualitative forecasting techniques are subjective, based on the opinion and judgment of consumers, experts; appropriate when past data is not available. It is usually applied to intermediate-long range decisions.

Example of qualitative forecasting methods:

- Informed opinion and judgment
- Delphi method
- Market research
- Historical life-cycle Analogy.

Quantitative forecasting models are used to estimate future demands as a function of past data; appropriate when past data is available. It is usually applied to short-intermediate range decisions.

Example of Quantitative forecasting methods:

- Last period demand
- Arithmetic Average
- Simple Moving Average (N-Period)
- Weighted Moving Average (N-period)
- Simple Exponential Smoothing
- Multiplicative Seasonal Indexes

Naïve Approach

Naïve forecasts are the most cost-effective and efficient objective forecasting model, and provide a benchmark against which more sophisticated models can be compared. For stable time series data, this approach says that the forecast for any period equals the previous period's actual value.

Time series methods

Time series methods use historical data as the basis of estimating future outcomes.

- Moving average
- Weighted moving average
- Exponential smoothing
- Autoregressive moving average (ARMA)
- Autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA)
 e.g. Box-Jenkins

- Extrapolation
- Linear prediction
- Trend estimation
- Growth curve

Causal / econometric forecasting methods

Some forecasting methods use the assumption that it is possible to identify the underlying factors that might influence the variable that is being forecast. For example, including information about weather conditions might improve the ability of a model to predict umbrella sales. This is a model of seasonality which shows a regular pattern of up and down fluctuations. In addition to weather, seasonality can also be due to holidays and customs such as predicting that sales in college football apparel will be higher during football season as opposed to the off season.

Casual forecasting methods are also subject to the discretion of the forecaster. There are several informal methods which do not have strict algorithms, but rather modest and unstructured guidance. One can forecast based on, for example, linear relationships. If one variable is linearly related to the other for a long enough period of time, it may be beneficial to predict such a relationship in the future. This is quite different from the aforementioned model of seasonality whose graph would more closely resemble a sine or

cosine wave. The most important factor when performing this operation is using concrete and substantiated data. Forecasting off of another forecast produces inconclusive and possibly erroneous results.

Such methods include:

- Regression analysis includes a large group of methods that can be used to predict future values of a variable using information about other variables. These methods include both **parametric** (linear or non-linear) and **non-parametric** techniques.
- Autoregressive moving average with exogenous inputs (ARMAX)

Judgmental methods

Judgmental forecasting methods incorporate intuitive judgements, opinions and subjective probability estimates.

- Composite forecasts
- Surveys
- Delphi method
- Scenario building
- Technology forecasting
- Forecast by analogy

Artificial intelligence methods

- Artificial neural networks
- Group method of data handling
- Support vector machine

Other methods

- Simulation
- Prediction market
- Probabilistic forecasting and Ensemble forecasting

- Reference class forecasting

Applications of forecasting

Forecasting has application in many situations:

- **Supply chain management** - Forecasting can be used in Supply Chain Management to make sure that the right product is at the right place at the right time. Accurate forecasting will help retailers reduce excess inventory and therefore increase profit margin. Studies have shown that extrapolations are the least accurate, while company earnings forecasts are the most reliable. Accurate forecasting will also help them meet consumer demand.
- Weather forecasting, Flood forecasting and Meteorology
- Transport planning and Transportation forecasting
- Economic forecasting
- Egain Forecasting
- Technology forecasting
- Earthquake prediction
- Land use forecasting
- Product forecasting
- Player and team performance in sports
- Telecommunications forecasting
- Political Forecasting
- Sales Forecasting

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